

Developing Library Leadership: Competency-Based Succession Planning

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Introduction

As academic libraries face a rapidly changing information landscape, the need for a sustainable succession plan has become increasingly urgent. Yet, despite growing awareness of the risks posed by an aging workforce and shifting professional demands, succession planning remains underdeveloped in many institutions. This chapter explores the key challenges that hinder effective succession planning in libraries, drawing from prevalent, peer-reviewed literature. Through this examination, this paper lays the groundwork for competency-based approaches that can support long-term organizational resilience.

Succession Planning Challenges in Libraries

A common concern across the library science literature is the impending wave of retirements among senior library staff and the resulting threat to institutional knowledge. Galbraith and Smith (2012), Arthur (1998), and Blakesley (2011) all underscore the urgency posed by an aging leadership demographic. The retirement of experienced professionals risks a significant loss of institutional memory and leadership expertise, making a proactive approach essential to ensure organizational continuity. Weare et al. (2015) reinforce this concern, noting that human resources experts have long anticipated that an aging workforce places libraries at risk of losing their most experienced workers—those who serve as informal knowledge custodians.

Several factors contribute to the weakness of succession planning. Galbraith et al. (2012) argue that it often lacks visibility and priority within institutional strategic planning processes. Additionally, Weare et al. (2015) point to a fundamental problem: the absence of empirical evidence demonstrating succession planning's effectiveness in academic libraries. This lack of validation contributes to ongoing skepticism regarding the value of succession planning as a

sustainable, long-term staffing strategy. Weare et al. (2015) also highlight another deeply embedded challenge: Rather than critically examining whether existing roles remain relevant, library institutions often focus on filling vacancies as they arise. The authors note, “library leaders would want to fill those same positions—some of which may no longer be ‘the right work’ for the current or future climate” (p. 335). This inclination to preserve the status quo limits opportunities to realign staffing structures with evolving institutional goals. This structural issue becomes particularly significant as libraries redefine their services in response to shifting patron expectations and technological advancements. Additionally, Charbonneau and Freeman (2016) emphasize that succession planning must be informed by a strategic vision that anticipates future needs rather than solely maintaining existing frameworks.

The Competency Framework Approach

The competency framework approach offers libraries a structured method for addressing succession planning challenges through systematic skill identification and development. In a study conducted by Beile and Adams (2000), they noted that library positions have traditionally been categorized along technical and non-technical lines, with distinct skill profiles emerging between these categories. Technical services positions increasingly require specialized skills such as prior work experience or computer proficiency. According to the authors, educational requirements are also shifting, with a noted relaxation in the universal requirement for an ALA-accredited MLS degree for some technical positions, particularly in electronic services. This evolution in job requirements reflects the changing nature of library work and the need for more diverse and specialized skill sets.

Ohio Library Council's Competency Model

The Ohio Library Council (OLC) (2019) developed a comprehensive competency model that maps essential skills across different library positions, creating a visual representation of how competencies are distributed throughout the organization. This framework establishes clear definitions for each competency, enabling consistent understanding and assessment.

Competency	Definition	Foundational	Adult Services	Children's Services	Circulation Services	Collection Development	Digital and Media Services	Director	Facilities and Maintenance	Fiscal Officer	Genealogy and Local History	Human Resources	Information Technology (IT)	Management & Administrative	Marketing and Public Relations	Outreach Services	Safety and Security	Technical Services	Teen Services	
Acquisition	The ability to effectively process library material orders; knowledge of vendor software, processes, products, and updates.					X							X						X	
Adaptability	The ability to adjust to changing situations.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Advocacy	The ability to promote and support the fundamental purpose of the public library.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Building Management	The knowledge and management of the library's building, grounds, and equipment.							X	X	X				X			X			
Cataloging and Metadata	The preparation of accurate descriptions of library materials and the provision of appropriate access.																		X	
Collection Management	The ability to select and evaluate materials and to maintain a collection designed to meet the needs of the intended audience, including conservation and preservation.		X	X		X	X				X					X		X	X	

Figure 1: An example of core competencies mapping with library staff developed by OLC (2019)

Universal, Common, and Specialized Competencies

A key insight from analyzing the Ohio Library Council's framework is the natural division of competencies into three distinct tiers: universal, common, and specialized. This tiered approach offers a strategic perspective for succession planning efforts. Universal Competencies form the foundation for all library staff, regardless of position, including adaptability, communication, and teamwork. Common Competencies represent the middle level of skills that are found in multiple but not all positions, including community engagement and innovation. Specialized Competencies

are the most narrowly distributed skills, often concentrated in leadership positions, including strategic planning and personnel management.

The tiered competency approach aligns with the recommendation from Weare et al. (2015) for "a continuous assessment of current and future personnel needs" (p. 348) as it focuses on developing transferable skills rather than simply preparing individuals for specific positions. This framework transforms succession planning from a position-focused activity to a competency-development process, allowing libraries to build organizational resilience through implementing widespread skill development strategies, addressing the "gap between understanding the importance of succession planning principles and the implementation and practice of these principles" (p. 222) identified by Galbraith et al. (2012).

Implementing Competency-Based Succession Planning

Central to effective succession planning is the development of leadership competencies, which are necessary since leadership positions are very critical to fill. The OLC model identifies "leadership" as a specialized competency that aligns with several core leadership skills from the Maternal and Child Health Public Health Leadership Institute (MCH PHLI) framework discussed by Fernandez et al. (2014), including self-awareness, communication, transformational leadership, and, most importantly, emotional intelligence. In practice, according to Kundanis (2014), effective implementation begins with a clear assessment of the library's current situation—analyzing strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Stakeholder engagement at all levels ensures inclusive planning, while a clear proposal outlining the value of succession planning helps initiate strategic discussions. Libraries should set goals aligned with their long-term vision, formalize succession strategies through policy integration, and establish mentoring programs to build a

future-ready talent pool. Additionally, ongoing communication, advocacy, and regular plan evaluations ensure that succession planning remains a dynamic, responsive process embedded in the library's culture. For the sake of this exercise, I will only delve into the assessment and gap analysis, as well as developing the skills necessary to make a pathway for a successful transition.

Assessment and Gap Analysis

The first critical step in implementing competency-based succession planning is conducting a thorough assessment of current competency distributions across the organization. Using frameworks like the OLC (2019) competency matrix, libraries can create a comprehensive inventory of skills present in their current workforce. This assessment reveals not only where competencies exist but also where critical gaps may emerge due to anticipated retirements or departures. Charbonneau and Freeman (2016) recommend building "an expertise database" as a key strategy for succession planning. This approach involves documenting which staff members possess which competencies, at what levels of proficiency, and how these align with current and future organizational needs. Gap analysis should specifically consider what Meier (2010) highlights as "the nature of a librarian's job is ever changing with new technology and the evolving information landscape" (p. 165). This means assessing not just current competency distributions but also anticipating which competencies will become increasingly important as library services evolve. This forward-looking assessment addresses Weare et al.'s (2015) concern about the risk of perpetuating "obsolete organizational structures" (p. 343) by ensuring development efforts align with future strategic directions rather than simply maintaining the status quo.

Development Pathways for Staff

Once competency gaps and needs are identified, libraries must create intentional development pathways for staff to mitigate the loss of expertise through proactive knowledge transfer and skill development. This requires moving beyond "training particular librarians to fill particular positions" (p. 339) that Galbraith et al. (2012) note is insufficient for comprehensive succession planning.

Effective development pathways should address the three tiers of competencies identified in the OLC framework:

1. **Universal Competency Development:** Ensuring all staff strengthen foundational skills like communication, adaptability, and problem-solving creates organizational resilience and prepares more individuals for potential advancement.
2. **Common Competency Cultivation:** Identifying staff with aptitude for "bridge competencies" like community engagement and innovation allows targeted development of those with leadership potential. Cross-training opportunities, project leadership roles, and mentoring can help staff develop these mid-tier competencies.
3. **Specialized Competency Transfer:** For the most critical and specialized competencies, implementing intentional knowledge transfer becomes essential. This might include job shadowing, documented processes, mentoring relationships, and graduated responsibility to ensure these rare skills aren't lost during transitions.

Implementation of these processes must also overcome the lack of prioritization of succession planning in strategic plans. This requires integrating competency development into performance management systems, allocating specific resources for development activities, and establishing

clear metrics for measuring progress, which is very critical. By systematically assessing competency distributions, identifying critical gaps, and creating intentional development pathways, libraries can implement succession planning that addresses the demographic challenges highlighted across the literature while remaining flexible enough to adapt to the evolving nature of library services.

Conclusion

Succession planning in academic libraries is not merely a staffing concern—it is a strategic imperative tied to the long-term vitality of the institution. As the profession grapples with an aging workforce, rapidly evolving user needs, and shifts in library work itself, it becomes clear that traditional approaches to the transition of positions are no longer sufficient. The literature reveals that while awareness of these challenges is widespread, implementation often falters. Competency-based succession planning offers a viable path forward by shifting the focus from specific positions to the development of transferable skills across organizational levels. Green (2018) addresses succession planning challenges proactively and emphasizes that libraries should focus on early career leadership development initiatives. It all begins with library science programs that can incorporate leadership coursework and dedicated management tracks into their curricula, ensuring graduates possess foundational leadership competencies before entering the workforce. Complementing classroom education with required internships and practical experiences allows students to apply leadership theory in real-world settings while building confidence. Post-graduation, librarian residency programs provide intensive rotation experiences across departments, exposing new professionals to various library functions while cultivating leadership skills. Throughout these educational and early career experiences, formal mentorship programs connecting emerging professionals with experienced library leaders can guide administrative

responsibilities and institutional knowledge transfer, creating a pipeline of leadership-ready professionals before succession needs become critical.

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